

Table 1. Average yield of rice (ROK 3) in uplands under different cropping systems. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1976 wet season.

Cropping system (no. of rice crops after bush fallow) ^a	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)		
		Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	
			60 kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha
1st	5	1.26	1.93	2.04
2d	4	0.77	1.87	2.05
3d	4	0.82	1.61	1.82

^aOne rice crop was grown per year.

Table 2. Effect of improved and traditional cultivation practices on the yield of a local rice variety. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1978 wet season.

District	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Yield increase (%) due to improved practices
		Improved practices	Traditional practices	
Kambia	5	1.82	0.90	101
Tonkolili	5	1.04	0.57	77
Bo	5	1.61	0.85	88
Moyamba	10	1.56	1.02	51
Kailahun	5	1.30	0.61	114
Kono	5	1.24	0.84	47

Table 3. Net returns on investment on fertilizer application to upland rice. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1978 wet season.^a

District	Net return (\$/\$1 investment)			
	60 kg N/ha	30 kg K/ha	60 kg N and 30 kg K/ha	60 kg N, 30 kg P, and 30 kg K/ha
Kambia	7.23	4.86	5.91	2.64
Bombali	3.63	7.94	4.90	5.38
Tonkolili	2.70	3.16	3.07	3.50
Kaoinadugu	3.30	7.80	0.78	0.71
Bo	1.87	5.39	1.05	1.07
Moyamba	7.00	20.35	8.81	5.09
Kailahun	4.41	26.92	6.37	3.01

^aPrice of 1 kg N = \$0.49, 1 kg P₂O₅ = \$0.70, 1 kg K₂O = \$0.25, and 1 kg rice grain = \$0.22.

In the first rice crop grown after bush fallow around Rokupr, the average rice yield with the application of 60–80 kg N/ha was 1.9–2.0 t/ha. The rice yield in the second and third year after bush fallow could be maintained at a similar level through the application of adequate amounts of fertilizers (Table 1). It is therefore not true that upland rice should not be grown in successive years on the same site.

The trials in farmers' fields to study the effect of improved practices included fertilizer application and line sowing. The results demonstrated that farmers' production with local varieties can be improved considerably through improved cultivation practices (Table 2).

The fertilizer response data collected from on-farm trials showed that investment on fertilizer was highly remunerative. Allowing for the risk of crop failures due to natural calamities and other costs in fertilizer application, a net profit of \$2 or more every \$1 investment can be considered remunerative (Table 3).

The results show that in the bush fallow-rice system, the application of either nitrogen or potassium, or both, gives high net returns in almost all districts. ■

Growth and yield of *Tilapia nilotica* fish and rice in irrigated paddies

M. Zahidul Hoque and Raisuddin Akanda, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

An experiment to determine the effect of two population densities (25,000 and 37,500) of *Tilapia nilotica* on the growth and yield of the fish as well as on rice yield was conducted in farmers' fields at

the BRRI Cropping Systems Research site at Salna in 1979 aus (Apr–Aug). The rice variety Chandina was transplanted with and without fish. Two trenches, each 1 m wide and 50 cm deep, were maintained across the middle of the paddies with fish. Well-prepared levees were maintained around the paddies. Fish were released into the field 5 days after transplanting (DT). Water depth was maintained at 5–10 cm until 25 DT and at 10–15 cm for the remainder of

the period.

The paddies without fish were kept flooded at a depth of 5–10 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 50 kg N/ha and 43 kg P₂O₅/ha. At 30 DT the water depth was reduced to about 2–4 cm, and nitrogen was topdressed.

The rice crop and the fish were harvested at 106 DT. The fish whose initial population was 25,000 increased 215% in number per hectare; each fish increased in size by 5 cm (see table). The

The influence of 2 population densities of fish on the number, size, and weight of fish and on rice yields. BRRI, 1979.

Population	Fish population (no./ha)			Fish size (cm)			Fish wt (kg/ha)			Rice yield (t/ha)	
	Initial	At harvest	Increase	Initial	At harvest	Increase	Initial	At harvest	Increase	With fish	Without fish
1	25,000	53,771	28,771	4.5	9.5	5.0	114	442	328	2.8	2.8
2	37,500	78,457	40,957	4.5	8.5	4.0	149	273	124	2.6	2.6
Mean	31,250	66,114	34,864	4.5	9.0	4.5	132	358	226	2.7	2.7

fish whose initial population was 37,500 increased in number by 209%; in size, each fish increased by 4 cm. Fish weight

increased considerably during the cropping duration. A higher population reduced the ultimate size of each

individual fish and the total fish yield per hectare. But fish culture had no appreciable effect on the rice yield. ■

March 7/23/80
Suitable cultivars for intensive rice-based cropping systems in Bangladesh

Md. Nazrul Islam Miah, M. Zahidul Hoque, and Peter R. Hobbs, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

The Rice Cropping Systems Division initiated research to evaluate and modify the essentially rice-based cropping systems of the BRRI project area. The cultivation of nonrice crops should be incorporated into the existing rice cropping systems to improve the potential cropping patterns for rainfed and irrigated areas. Unfortunately, suitable cultivars for many nonrice crops were not available from local sources. BRRI has no mandate to develop varieties other than those of rice, so the division undertook a

Promising cultivars for intensive rice-based multiple cropping systems. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Crops	Best performing cultivars	Potentially acceptable cultivars
Field corn	Thai Comp., No. 1 DMR BC ₃ (S) C1, Early DMR Comp. 2	Thai Comp., No. 1 (S) C ₂ , Early DMR Comp. 1
Sweet corn	Thai Comp. supersweet DMR #1	College sweet synthetic
Sorghum	IS2940, Cosor 2	CS108, Cosor 3, CS100
Pearl millet	ICRISAT-7141NEP-13-5007-2 (OP)	ICRISAT-7142NEP-13-5613-1 (OP)
Peanut	Kidang, SK-38	CES101, P23, EG. Bunchy
Soybean	Davis, Williams (dry season) Bossier, Hardee, Seemes (wet season)	Clark 63, TK5 Williams, Davis
Chickpea	ICRISAT No. 4951, 2784	2836, 4961, 4465
Cowpea	All season	TVU354, TVU201, RDC-6-12W

varietal screening program with active participation of relevant national and international organizations.

From 1974 to 1978, varieties of corn, sorghum, pearl millet, peanut, soybean, cowpea, and chickpea were evaluated at

the BRRI experimental farms and in selected farmers' fields of the BRRI project area. Several promising varieties were identified (see table) and are now used in various single and double cropping systems in the area. ■

March 7/23/80
Evaluation of mung bean cultivars under monoculture and intercropping systems

Md. Nazrul Islam Miah, research fellow; and Virgilio R. Carañgal, network coordinator, Cropping Systems Program, Multiple Cropping Department, International Rice Research Institute

The pulse crop mung bean *Vigna radiata* is grown mostly as monoculture but is

also intercropped with corn and sugarcane or grown under plantation crops such as coconut or rubber. Mung bean is also relayed in wetland rice in most of Southeast Asia. Evaluation of mung bean varieties for varied conditions is imperative because of yield fluctuations due to seasonal and environmental situations. An important question is whether breeders should evaluate varieties

in monoculture or in intercropping systems for maximum testing efficiency.

Ten mung bean varieties were evaluated in monoculture and intercropped with corn in dry- and wet-season trials in 1978-79 at the new upland area of the IRRI experimental farm. Recommended cultural management practices, such as fertilization, weeding, irrigation, and

Yield comparison (kg/ha) of mung bean varieties and their relative ranking for monoculture and when intercropped with corn. IRRI, 1978-79 dry season and 1979 wet season.^a

Mung bean variety	1978-79 dry season				1979 wet season			
	Monoculture yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Intercrop yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Monoculture yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Intercrop yield (kg/ha)	Rank
EG-MG-174-3	850 a	1	203	2	873 abc	5	465 abc	6
CES 55	638 ab	2	213	1	779 bc	8	377 c	8
S8 (Green)	619 b	3	160	5	671 c	10	363 c	9
M350	601 b	4	135	7	1055 a	2	525 abc	4
CES-1T-2	589 b	5	178	3	1061 a	1	667 a	1
CES-14	561 b	6	137	6	821 abc	7	387 bc	7
CES-U-1	534 b	7	168	4	694 c	9	315 c	10
MG-50-10A (Y)	490 b	8	115	10	1024 ab	3	478 abc	5
CES-1D-21	475 b	9	127	9	877 abc	4	611 a	2
CES-1F-5	449 b	10	129	8	871 abc	6	598 ab	3
Mean	580		157 ns		873		478	
CV (%)	23		42		18		21	

^ans = not significant. In a column means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.